

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization DISEASE RESISTANCE

Reaction of rice genotypes to stem rot (SR) fungi and bacterial blight (BB) pathogen

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SR caused by three species of *Sclerotium* (*S. oryzae*, *S. hydrophyllum*, and *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare*) and BB caused by *Xanthomonas campestris* pv. *oryzae* (Ishiyama) Dye are the major rice diseases in Haryana. We evaluated 125 early to medium duration rices against SR and BB at HAURRS, during 1984-85 kharif.

Each test entry was planted in two 2-m-long rows, at 20- × 15- cm spacing. Plants were clip-inoculated with BB suspension at 21 d after transplanting (DT) for kresek and at 45 DT for leaf blight, and scored for resistance at 30 and 14 d after inoculation. SR screening was done in the field as well as in the laboratory. In the field, disease incidence was recorded at maturity when disease development was highest and scored by the *Standard evaluation system for rice* (1980).

In the laboratory, cut stem pieces were wound-inoculated with a small piece of agar-cultured *S. oryzae*, *S. hydrophyllum*, and *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare* separately at booting. The

inoculated stems were set upright in a test tube rack in a tray with 2.5 cm of water. They were covered with plastic bags to retain moisture and incubated at 28-30° C. Lesion length was measured 10 d after inoculation. Entries with lesions less than 10 mm long were considered resistant; those with 10-30 mm lesions, moderately resistant; and those with more than 30 mm, susceptible.

In the laboratory screening, the location severity index (LSI) was 5.97% for *S. oryzae*, 3.46 for *S. hydrophyllum*, and 7.63 for *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare*. In field tests, LSI was 5.51 for SR, 5.78 for kresek, and 5.10 for leaf blight.

Of the entries tested, 11 entries showed resistance to the combination of *S. oryzae* and *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare*, 10 to *S. hydrophyllum* and *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare*, 28 to *S. oryzae* and *S. hydrophyllum*, and 9 to the 3 *Sclerotium* spp. (Table 1). Against BB, 13 entries showed resistance to the kresek phase and 76 to the leaf blight phase. Of nine entries showing resistance to the three *Sclerotium* spp., all except BR51-331-4 exhibited resistance to the blight phase. RP2151-175-1 and RP2151-192-1 need special mention as they had a resistance to all the *Sclerotium* spp. in the laboratory and in the field and also to both phases of BB (Table 2). *J*

Table 1. Reaction of rice varieties to SR fungi *Sclerotium oryzae*, *S. hydrophyllum*, and *S. oryzae* var. *irregulare*. HAURRS, Haryana, India, 1984-85.

Resistant to <i>S. oryzae</i> and <i>S. oryzae</i> var. <i>irregulare</i>	
HAU39-4020-3, HAU119-362, BR51-331-4, BR52-90-2, RP2151-166-4-1, RP2151-175-1, RP2151-192-1, RP2151-192-2-5, RP2151-221-4-2-4, RP2151-224-1, and CR318-548-7.	
Resistant to <i>S. hydrophyllum</i> and <i>S. oryzae</i> var. <i>irregulare</i>	
HAU118-104, BR51-331-4, RP2151-166-4-1, RP2151-166-4-4-1, RP2151-175-1, RP2151-192-1, RP2151-192-2-5, RP2151-221-4-2-4, RP2151-224-4, and CR318-548-4-2-4.	
Resistant to <i>S. oryzae</i> and <i>S. hydrophyllum</i>	
HAU47-3888-2, HAU118-77, HAU118-106, HAU118-108, HAU118-109, HAU118-110, HAU118-111, HAU118-141, HAU118-162, HAU118-183, HAU118-184, HAU118-186, HAU118-206, HAU118-222, HAU118-782, HAU119-309, HAU119-800, HAU120-337, IR9784-142-1-3-3, BR51-331-4, CR318-548-7, RP2135-51-1, RP2151-166-4-1, RP2151-166-4-4-1, RP2151-192-1, RP2151-192-2-5, RP2151-221-4-2-4, and RP2151-224-4.	
Resistant to 3 <i>Sclerotium</i> spp.	
BR51-331-4, RP2151-1664-1, RP2151-16644-1, RP2151-175-1, RP2151-192-1, RP2151-192-2-5, RP2151-221-4-2-4, RP2151-224-4, and CR318-548-7.	

Table 2. Reaction to SR, and kresek and leaf blight phases of BB in field of entries with resistance to 3 *Sclerotium* spp. HAURRS, Haryana, India, 1984-85.

Entry	Parentage	Reaction ^a to		
		Kresek	Leaf blight	Stem rot
BR51-331-4	IR20/IR5-114-3-1	S	S	R
CR318-548-7	IET4141/CR98-7216	MR	R	MR
RP2151-166-4-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	MR	R	R
RP2151-166-4-4-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	MR	R	R
RP2151-175-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	R	R	R
RP2151-192-1	IET4141/CR98-7216	R	R	R
RP2151-192-2-5	IET4141/CR98-7216	S	R	R
RP2151-221-4-2-4	IET4141/CR98-7216	MR	R	R
RP2151-224-4	IET4141/CR98-7216	MR	R	MR

^aR = resistant (score of 3 or lower), MR = moderately resistant (5), and S = susceptible (7-9).

Reaction of rice cultivars to bacterial blight (BB)

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BB is a major rice disease in the Tarai region of Nepal. In 1985 kharif, 117 rice cultivars were evaluated for reaction to BB.

Each entry was transplanted into earthen pots 21 d after sowing. At maximum tillering, plants were clip-inoculated with a BB suspension from

leaf extract. At 14 d after inoculation, they were scored for resistance using the *Standard evaluation system for rice (SES)*. Of 117 entries, 26 were resistant (see table). For the remaining 91, susceptibility ranged from moderate to high. *ℳ*

Varietal reaction to BB at IAAS, Rampur, Nepal, 1985.

Cultivar	Score ^a
Tetep	1.0
BG379-2	1.0
Nigeria 5	1.0
DV85	1.0
IR19661-63-1-2-3	1.0
BG400-1	3.0
IR8608-82-1-3-1-3	3.0
C 1321-9	3.0
ADT36	3.0
BPT3291	3.0
IR19083-22-2-2	3.0
Taichung Sen 1	3.0
BR153-21-10-1-3	3.0
Se 322B-19	3.0
BG367-4	3.0
IR2307-247-2-2-3	3.0
IR5873-9-1	3.0
IR50	3.0
IR9171-60-2-2	3.0
IR2725-63-2-2	3.0
IR36	3.0
IR21820-154-3-2-2-3	3.0
Chainung Sen Yu 29	3.0
IR62	3.0
Thapani	3.0
Saeto Anadi	3.0
TN1 (check)	9.0

^aBy the 1980 SES scale.

Genetic divergence and multiple disease resistance studies in rice (*Oryza sativa* L.)

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Genetic divergence is one criterion in selecting parents to generate crosses that give transgressive segregants in later generations. A parental divergence study was undertaken with released varieties and 120 elite lines (94 semidwarf, 24 intermediate, and 2 tall) primarily selected for their bacterial blight (BB) tolerance. The lines were from IRRI (55), India (42), Bangladesh (10),

Indonesia (5), 2 each from USA, Taiwan, and Sri Lanka, and 1 each from Thailand and the Philippines. The crop was grown under recommended agronomic practices in 1977 wet season (WS) at Pantnagar in a randomized block design with three replications. Each line had a 4-m² plot and 20 × 15-cm spacing. Mahalanobis D² statistics was used to study genetic divergence based on six characters: day to 50% flowering, plant height, effective tillers per plant, grain weight, grains per panicle, and grain yield (14% moisture) per plot. The lines were grouped in 18 clusters per Tocher's method suggested by Rao.

The lines were also screened for BB resistance in WS 1977, 1978, and 1979 at Pantnagar (29°N, 79.3°E, and 243.8 m mean sea level); for leaf blast at Majhera District, Nainital, in hills (29.28°N, 79.32° E, and 900 m); and for brown spot at Ranichauri (30.18°N, 78.290° E, and 2000 m) using the *Standard*

evaluation system for rice scale. Eleven lines showed multiple resistance to all three diseases.

Clustering pattern revealed five clusters (see table). One or two lines were further selected from each cluster on the basis of their higher grain yield, effective tillers, grain weight, hulling and milling percentage, and desirable alkali digestion value. IR2070-414-3-9 and BGW-2 in cluster I, IR22 in cluster V, and IR2415-904-3 in cluster VII were most desirable. The intercluster distance revealed that cluster VIII and IX were most divergent, followed by V and VIII, and VII and IX. BKN68 19-33-3-2-1-3 and IR2328-300-2-2 had higher divergence than most entries. The cross combination IR2328-300-2-2 and BKN6819-33-3-2-1-3 had maximum divergence followed by IR22 and IR2328-300-2-2. These crosses can be used to further select recombinants with multiple resistance, higher yield, and other desirable traits. *ℳ*

Intracluster and intercluster D² value in 5 selected clusters and the multiple-resistance lines in each cluster. 1977-79, Bihar, India.

Cluster	D ² value in different clusters					Multiple-resistance lines
	I	V	VII	VIII	IX	
I	28.2	75.7	51.5	188.0	152.0	IR2070-414-3-9 BG90-2 RP633-519-1-3-4-1 IR2071-527-3-1-3 IR2328-27-3-6 IR22
V		36.3	134.2	380.7	216.6	IR2415-90-4-3 IR2863-39-2 IR5491-4-80
VII			24.6	99.8	272.4	IR2328-300-2-2 IR2328-300-2-2 BKN6819-33-3-2-1-3
VIII				28.7	449.7	
IX					13.9	

Genetic Evaluation and Utilization INSECT RESISTANCE

Promising rice cultivars with combined resistance to gall midge (GM) and brown planthopper (BPH)

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Breeding for multiple resistance to pests is being emphasized for yield stability in

modern varieties. In 1984 kharif (Jun-Jul to Oct-Nov), we evaluated 45 entries from the AICRIP 1983 multiple resistance screening trial against GM in the field. Outbreak conditions were induced by close spacing (10 × 15 cm), adjusting planting time to 20 Jul to coincide with maximum infestation of the season, applying high N rates (100 + 25 + 25 g N/ha at 0, 15, and 30 d after